

Guarantees/Collateral in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions: Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics around Guarantees/Collateral in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions with a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word "Guarantee/Collateral" within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Guarantees/Collateral based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that there are 358 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding guarantees/collateral in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics around guarantees, whether frequently or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Guarantee; Collateral; Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions; Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer

Introduction

Banking is one of the main drivers of national development, because banking has an important role in collecting money from the public in the form of savings and then channeling it back to the community as consumptive and productive financing.

The banking system known as sharia banking was formed using Islamic law as its rationale. Customers and Islamic banks have a contractual relationship that regulates the legal relationship between the two. The word "contract" has the same meaning as "agreement" in English. The word "contract" which comes from Arabic, "Al-Aqdun", means a bond or knot on a rope. According to Islamic law, a contract is an agreement between an offer (ijab) and acceptance (qabul) which is supported by syara'.

Collateral or guarantees are realized as a result of a financing agreement between customers who own capital (shahibul maal) and business actors (mudharib). Collateral is needed to guarantee the return of bank money because the contract imposes an obligation on the business actor (mudharib) to return the borrowed funds. However, sometimes there are difficulties in returning the funds, one of which is the customer's carelessness in returning the funds.

According to Article 1233 of the Criminal Code, every agreement is made either by agreement or through the application of law. Agreements are a source of obligations. Therefore, the contract is a source of engagement. Therefore,

whatever the parties decide must be considered a conscious and voluntary agreement reached in accordance with their wishes. Article 1313 of the Criminal Code reaffirms this provision by stating that an agreement is an act by which a person binds himself to one or more other people.

Scientific articles about guarantees and collateral in Islamic banks are often published every year. From 2001 to 2022, there are 456 studies on guarantees and collateral in sharia banking available on Digital Reference Guard (Garuda). This shows the high interest of researchers in the study of guarantees and collateral in Islamic banking.

The aim of this research is to map research topics around collateral/collateral use library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics surrounding collateral, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics around guarantees, whether frequently or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Theoretical review

The Banking Law of 1992 recognizes legal terms (collateral) and technical terms (collateral). The meaning of the word guarantee in this Law is different from that in Law no. 14 of 1967. Meanwhile, Law no. 14 of 1967 defines collateral as collateral, Law no. 7 of 1992 explains the meaning of guarantee as a teaching about ability and capability. The objects intended and desired by Article 1131 of the Civil Code Law are: "All collectible assets, whether involved or not involved, whether existing or which will exist in the future, are the responsibility of all obligations.

Sharia financial inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit riba (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Sharia financial inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of sharia financial inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Sharia financial inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, sharia financial inclusion also supports the development of the sharia financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of literature study research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, literature study research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and

organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications.

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology.

Research methods

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library research. The object of the research is Guarantee or Collateral in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Guarantees or Collateral originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keywords "Guarantee", "Collateral", and "Collateral" within the entire year (20 01 - 2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics, methods, research findings, and research space based on library research studies.

Results and Discussion

The results of searches for scientific publications regarding Guarantees or Collateral for 22 years, namely from 2001 to 2022, show growth in journal publications every year, especially over the last 9 years. There are 424 article titles published in accredited national and international journals. In 2019 alone there were 57 articles published, so that every year more than 40 research articles on Guarantees and Collateral are published.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Guarantees or Collateral by year

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2001	1	2011	2	2017	37
2005	1	2012	4	2018	62
2006	2	2013	28	2019	57
2007	1	2014	29	2020	42
2009	2	2015	21	2021	50
2010	1	2016	45	2022	39
Number of Publication Articles 424					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 2 shows that there are 14 affiliates/institutions that publish the most research articles about Guarantees or Collateral. The Law Faculty Student Journal is the journal publishing institution that publishes the most research results regarding Guarantees, with a total of 36 articles.

Table 2. Journal of publishers of scientific publications regarding Guarantees/Collateral

Name of Institution/Affiliation	Number of Publications
Law Faculty Student Journal	36
Collection of Law Faculty Student Journals	35
Premise Law Journal	22
Kertha Semaya: Journal of Legal Studies	17
Lex Privatum	11
Private Law Journal	10
Diponegoro Law Journal	9
USU Civil Law Journal	8

Indonesian Notary	7
Dynamics	6
Student Scientific Journal for Civil Law	5
DiH: Journal of Legal Studies	4
Advocacy Scientific Journal	3
Al-Intaj: Journal of Sharia Economics and Banking	2

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

The most productive researchers who write journals about collateral/collateral have an average of 2 articles. They are: Atika (Sebelas Maret University), Atika, Kiafsy Agstaiamy Sitorus (North Sumatra State University), Amanda Feby Fitrayani, Akhmad Budi Cahyo (University of Indonesia), Fitriaty Pangerang (Ujung Pandang State Polytechnic), Muhammad Hatta Pramata (Brawijaya University), I Made Sudirga (Udayana University), Emy Andayani Citra, I Made Sudirga (Mahasaraswati University Denpasar), Muhammad Yusuf Ibrahim (Muhammadiyah University Purwokerto), (Abdurachman Saleh University Situbondo). Meanwhile, other researchers only wrote 1 journal article.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research Regarding Guarantees or Collateral in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Search results for research articles via the Garuda website (Digital Referral Garba) are sent in the form of a Research Information System (RIS), entered and described using VOSViewer. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Depiction of the relationship map of research development regarding Guarantees or Collateral

Source: Data processed, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

Based on the results of the analysis, it shows a network visualization in the form of a co-word map of the development of research regarding Guarantees into 7 clusters and 206 topics, namely as follows:

- Cluster 1. The red color consists of 41 topics, namely: ability, bank guarantee, sharia banking, banking, basis, business, capacity, character, client, collateral, community, company, contract, credit, customer, decision, development, economy, employee, bank, financing, government, guarantee, guarantor, insurance, Islamic bank, obligation, financing, population, position, principle, product, provision, requirement, risk, role, significant effect, society, type, UMKM, unsecured loan.
- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 28 topics, namely: agreement, agreement, article, case approach, certificate, court, creditor, debt, debtor, debtor default, developer, execution, implementation, issue, legal consequence, lending, loan agreement, mechanism, money, mortgage, mortgage guarantee, object, observation, problem, procedure, purchase, stage, transfer.
- Cluster 3. The blue color consists of 20 topics, namely: addition, appraisal, bank, bank credit agreement, conceptual approach, credit contract, economic value, fiduciary, fiduciary collateral, fiduciary collateral object, fiduciary guarantee, fiduciary guarantee, law number, legal research, normative legal research, obstacle, property, registration, responsibility, value.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 17 topics, namely: additional guarantee, asset, civil code, data collection technique, debtor, district court, effectiveness, existence, law, legal protection, legislation, loss, personal guarantee, primary data, protection, secondary data, settlement.
- Cluster 5. The green color consists of 16 topics, namely: collateral, auction, bad credit, people's credit banks, banking law, debtors, guarantees, guaranteed rights, credit, bad credit, creditors, qualitative, credit, settlement of bad credit, credit agreements, third party.
- Cluster 6. The black color consists of 14 topics, namely: independent bank, Indonesian people's bank, state savings bank, building, credit agreement, credit facility, credit guarantee, encumbrance, hypothecation, credit guarantee, persero, pledge, process, repayment.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Guarantees/Collateral in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions

Library Research in previous research journals, researchers found 358 Research topics regarding guarantees/collateral in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions, namely:

- JURIDICAL REVIEW OF MOTORCYCLES AS COLLATERAL IN WARRANTY INSTITUTIONS
- ASSESSMENT OF CREDIT COLLATERAL WITH GREEN LETTER STATUS
- MODEL FOR DETERMINING THE ELIGIBILITY OF PROVIDING CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL AT BANK MANDIRI
- Evaluation of the Internal Control System for Accepting and Storing Collateral at Pegadaian Companies

- MASTERING THE DOCUMENTS AND BINDING THE COLLATERAL WITH A POWER OF ATTORNEY CHARGES THE RIGHTS OF CREDIT IN PROVIDING EXPLOITATION CREDIT
- DEVELOPMENT OF INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY RIGHTS AS COLLATERAL (COLLATERAL) TO OBTAIN BANKING CREDIT IN INDONESIA
- DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM FOR GRANTING CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL (KTA) IN STANDARD CHARTERED BANK
- Settlement of Bad Credit on Unsecured Credit at PT. Bank CIMB Niaga, Tbk. Semarang Branch
- ANALYSIS OF COLLATERAL VALUE FROM MARKET VALUE AND RENTAL VALUE OF A RESIDENCE HOUSE ON AW SYAHRANIE STREET SAMARINDA CITY, EAST KALIMANTAN PROVINCE
- SETTLEMENT OF BAD CREDIT IN CREDIT AGREEMENTS WITH COLLATERAL DEEDS OF SALE AND PURCHASE WITHOUT MONEY RIGHTS (Study at PT. Bank Rakyat Indonesia Tbk, Turen Unit)
- SETTLEMENT OF DEFAULTS IN PROVIDING CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PROVISION OF REVOLVING FUNDS AND MICRO CREDIT FOR THE MANDIRI NATIONAL COMMUNITY EMPOWERMENT PROGRAM (PNPM) (Study in Jambangan Village, Besuk District, Probolinggo Regency)
- Analysis of the Collateral Value of Residential Houses in Medokan Asri Utara XII Surabaya
- IMPLEMENTATION OF CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL IN THE EVENT OF DEBTORS IN DEFAULT AT PT BANK OVERSEAS CHINESE BANKING CORPORATION (OCBC) NISP TBK DENPASAR BRANCH
- ANALYSIS OF INTERNAL CONTROL PROVIDING CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL (KTA) IN RELATION TO DETERMINING CREDIT RISK AT PT. BANK MANDIRI (Persero) Tbk SUDIRMAN PALEMBANG BRANCH
- FOREIGNED COLLATERAL (AYDA) ON BAD CREDIT AT PT. BPR TATA ANJUNG SARI
- DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM FOR GRANTING CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL (KTA) IN STANDARD CHARTERED BANK
- EXISTENCE OF COLLATERAL IN SHARIA COMMERCIAL BANK FINANCING IN DENPASAR
- PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS OF COMPANY FINANCIAL STATEMENTS AND COLLATERAL ASSESSMENT IN DECISIONS TO GIVE WORKING CAPITAL CREDIT TO PT BANK RAKYAT INDONESIA (PERSERO) TBK MANADO BRANCH
- APPLICATION OF PRUDENTIAL PRINCIPLES IN PROVIDING CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL AS AN EFFORT TO PREVENT BAD CREDIT AT THE REPUBLIC OF INDONESIA EMPLOYEE COOPERATIVE CENTER (PKPRI) MALANG CITY
- LEGAL PROTECTION FOR CREDITORS IN PROVIDING WORKING CAPITAL CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL
- IMPLEMENTATION OF MICRO CREDIT WITH CERTIFICATE COLLATERAL WITHOUT MONEY RIGHTS IN BLITAR DISTRICT
- Analysis of Collateral Value for Residential Houses Jl. Gebang Lor No. 62 Surabaya

- IMPLEMENTATION OF LEGAL PROTECTION FOR CREDITORS IN PROVIDING WORKING CAPITAL CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL (Study at Danamon Savings and Loans Unit Turen)
- OPTIMIZATION OF THE ECONOMIC VALUE OF BRAND RIGHTS INTO CREDIT COLLATERAL IN BANK (Critical Study of Legislation in the field of Intellectual Property Rights, Banking and Fiduciary)
- Analysis of the Collateral Value of Residential Houses in Permata Jingga Housing Block Teratai No. 12 Malang
- The Influence of Attitudes and Subjective Norms on Customer Intentions in Choosing Unsecured Credit at Bank Permata Denpasar Branch
- Identification of Social Capital in an Unsecured Financing System (Study at the Pandawa Cooperative, Sukun District, Malang City)
- COLLATERAL LAW IN ISLAMIC ECONOMICS
- THE INFLUENCE OF SERVICE SATISFACTION ON CUSTOMER DECISIONS TO USE UNCOLLATERAL CREDIT
- Application of the Decision Tree Algorithm for Assessing Collateral for Credit Applications
- Legal Aspects of Credit Agreements with Ship Collateral
- COOPERATION AGREEMENT BETWEEN BANK AND PUBLIC APPRAISAL SERVICES (KJPP) IN TERMS OF HOME OWNERSHIP CREDIT COLLATERAL ASSESSMENT (A RESEARCH AT PT. BANK CIMB NIAGA TBK, MEDAN BUKIT BARISAN BRANCH)
- DEBTOR'S OBLIGATION TO INSURE COLLATERAL GOODS WITH MOUNTING RIGHTS IN CREDIT AGREEMENTS AT PUBLIC AND PRIVATE BANKS
- EFFECTIVENESS OF PROVIDING CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL IN COMMERCIAL BANKS
- THE RIGHTS OF THE INDONESIAN NATION'S LAND OWNERSHIP SYSTEM AND ITS RELATIONSHIP TO THE APPLICATION OF DERIVATIVE RIGHTS IN THE FRAMEWORK OF COLLATERAL DEBT
- IMPLEMENTATION OF THE GRANTING OF PEOPLE'S BUSINESS CREDIT (KUR) WITHOUT COLLATERAL BASED ON THE REGULATION OF THE COORDINATING MINISTER FOR ECONOMIC AFFAIRS OF THE REPUBLIC OF INDONESIA NUMBER 8 OF 2015 AT PT BANK RAKYAT INDONESIA TABANAN BRANCH OFFICE PEREAN UNIT
- EXECUTION OF BAD CREDIT AT DANAMON BANK REGARDING CREDIT AGREEMENTS WITHOUT COLLATERAL IN SEMARANG DISTRICT
- LEGAL PROTECTION AGAINST CREDITORS WHO PROVIDE CREDIT LOANS WITHOUT COLLATERAL (STUDY OF BANK BNI BALIGE BRANCH)
- RESPONSIBILITIES OF PUBLIC APPRAISAL SERVICES IN DETERMINING THE VALUE OF COLLATERAL FOR LAND AND BUILDINGS THAT ARE MONEY RIGHTS
- APPLICATION OF ARTICLE 3 BANK INDONESIA REGULATION NO. 17/10/PBI/2015 CONCERNING LOAN TO VALUE FOR PROPERTY CREDIT REGARDING CREDIT CALCULATIONS AND COLLATERAL VALUE IN RESIDENTIAL HOUSE LOANS (Study at Bank BTN Cab. Malang)
- BINDING OF CREDIT AGREEMENTS AND COLLATERAL

- IMPLEMENTATION OF ARTICLE 10 REGULATION OF THE COORDINATING MINISTER FOR ECONOMIC AFFAIRS NUMBER 8 OF 2015 CONCERNING GUIDELINES FOR IMPLEMENTING PEOPLE'S BUSINESS CREDIT RELATED TO ADDITIONAL COLLATERAL WITHOUT AGREEMENT (Study at BRI Bank Kartini Blitar Unit)
- ANALYSIS OF PROBLEM CREDIT SETTLEMENT ON IMMOVABLE PROPERTY COLLATERAL (Study at PT Bank Mandiri Tbk. Micro Unit, Probolinggo Kraksaan Branch)
- JURIDICAL ANALYSIS OF APARTMENT UNIT SALE AND PURCHASE BINDING AGREEMENTS (PPJB) AS COLLATERAL IN INVESTMENT CREDIT AGREEMENTS (STUDY AT PT. BANK NATIONALNOBU TBK)
- JURIDICAL ANALYSIS OF PNS DECREES WHICH ARE USED AS COLLATERAL IN BANKING CREDIT AGREEMENTS REVIEWED FROM LAW NUMBER 10 OF 1998 CONCERNING BANKING (STUDY AT PT. BANK SUMUT IMAM BONJOL MEDAN)
- THE INFLUENCE OF INDIVIDUAL CHARACTER, BUSINESS AND COLLATERAL ON THE RATE OF RETURN ON MICRO BUSINESS CREDIT AT PT. BANK MANDIRI (PERSERO) TBK. KCM PURI NIRWANA
- ASSESSMENT OF PROPERTY COLLATERAL APPLICATION FOR CREDIT USING SUPPORT VECTOR MACHINE ALGORITHM BASED ON PARTICLE SWARM OPTIMIZATION
- LEGAL CERTAINTY OF COPYRIGHT VALUE AS A COLLATERAL OBJECT IN BANKING CREDIT APPLICATIONS
- BANK JURIDICAL CONSIDERATIONS IN DETERMINING HOW TO HANDLE PROBLEMS OF CREDIT WITH MOUNTING RIGHTS (Study at Bank Danamon, Pasar Berbek branch, Nganjuk Regency)
- DESIGN AND BUILDING OF COLLATERAL DATA AND BUSINESS LEGALITY DATA INFORMATION SYSTEMS AT BNI MAMUJU BRANCH
- DESIGN AND CONSTRUCTION OF A CUSTOMER COLLATERAL INSURANCE DATA INFORMATION SYSTEM IN THE SMALL CREDIT CENTER (SKC) SECTION OF BNI CAB PARE-PARE
- The Role of Collateral Use in Islamic Banks in Relation to the Sharia Banking Operational System in Medan
- The Role of Notaries in Binding Collateral with Mortgage Rights (Case Study at KSPPS BMT Bahtera Pekalongan City)
- Limits on Flats Used as Collateral with Banks
- PROBLEMATICS OF PROVIDING CREDIT BASED ON COLLATERAL WITH CAMAT SK STATUS AND NOTARY NOTE COVER (CASE STUDY AT PT. BANK RAKYAT INDONESIA (PERSERO), TBK LUBUK PAKAM BRANCH
- SETTLEMENT OF CREDIT PROBLEMS THROUGH AUCTION OF COLLATERAL CASE STUDY AT PT. BANK OF SUMUT MAIN BRANCH MEDAN
- IMPLEMENTATION OF CO-OWNED LAND AGREEMENTS AS COLLATERAL FOR CREDIT IN BANK BASED ON LAW NUMBER 4 OF 1996 CONCERNING MONITORY RIGHTS TO LAND AND OBJECTS RELATING TO LAND
- RESOLUTION OF COLLATERAL BINDING DISPUTES IN MURABAHAH FINANCING IN SHARIA BANK
- JURIDICAL IMPLICATIONS PHOTOCOPY OF DECISION LETTER ON APPOINTMENT OF CIVIL SERVANTS WHICH ARE LEGALIZED AS

- COLLATERAL IN BANK CREDIT AGREEMENTS (STUDY AT PT BANK PERKREDITAN RAKYAT ASHI, BADUNG DISTRICT, BALI PROVINCE)
- SOLVING CREDIT PROBLEMS WITHOUT COLLATERAL (UMKM) IN DENPASAR
 - Analysis of Islamic Law on Ijarah Agreements in Multipurpose Financing Without Collateral in the Sharia Financial Services Cooperative (KJKS) BMT Bee Mass Ngawi
 - Juridical Review of Notary/PPAT Covernotes Regarding Installation of Bank Collateral Mortgage Rights
 - LEGAL PROTECTION FOR CREDITORS AGAINST COLLATERAL OBJECTS USING A POWER OF SALE IF THE POWER DEADS
 - RESOLUTION OF COLLECTIVE PROPERTY DISPUTES WITH COLLATERAL STATUS IN DIVORCE CASES IN STATE COURT
 - Empowerment of MSMEs Based on Collateral Assessment as an Effort to Increase Access to Banking
 - ANALYSIS OF THE ACCOUNTING SYSTEM FOR PROVIDING HOUSE COLLATERAL CREDIT (KAR) AT PT. STATE SAVINGS BANK MANADO BRANCH OFFICE
 - THE LEGAL ASPECT OF CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL IN INDONESIA (LEGAL ASPECT OF CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL IN INDONESIA)
 - TRAINING TO MAKE A BUSINESS PLAN TAKES POSDAYA MERGOSINGO AND POSDAYA TAMAN RAJUT TO RECEIVE LOW INTEREST LOANS AND WITHOUT COLLATERAL FROM THE DAMANDIRI FOUNDATION TO DEVELOP THE BUSINESS
 - Limits on flats used as collateral for banks
 - SETTLEMENT OF BAD CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL IN THE AID PROVISION AGREEMENT IN THE NATIONAL PROGRAM FOR EMPOWERING INDEPENDENT RURAL COMMUNITIES (PNPM-MP) DHAMASRAYA DISTRICT
 - REGULATIONS ON THE USE OF ORDER LETTERS IN THE PROCESS OF BINDING CREDIT COLLATERAL IN THE FORM OF MORTGAGE RIGHTS
 - REVIEW ON THE IMPLEMENTATION OF AUCTIONS FOR MONITORED COLLATERAL RIGHTS IN BAD CREDIT CASES (STUDY RULING NUMBER 86/PDT/2015/PT.MDN)
 - The Effect of Lack of Collateral and Fines on Customer Interest in BMT UGT Sidogiri Pare Branch
 - ANALYSIS OF THE APPLICATION OF ACCOUNTING INFORMATION SYSTEMS IN CREDIT SYSTEMS WITH COLLATERAL AT PT. PEOPLE'S CREDIT BANK (BPR) MAROBA ITE BENGKULU BRANCH
 - DATA MINING CUSTOMER CLASSIFICATION IN APPLYING FOR CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL WITH THE K-NEAREST NEIGHBOR ALGORITHM (CASE STUDY: PT. BPR DIORI GANDA)
 - JURIDICAL ANALYSIS OF PROVIDING EMPLOYEE CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL AT PONTIANAK CITY MARKET BANK
 - Use of Collateral in Sharia Bank Musyarakah Agreements According to Law Number 21 of 2008 concerning Sharia Banking
 - LEGAL PROTECTION FOR CREDITORS HOLDING MORTGAGE RIGHTS AGAINST COLLATERAL DISPUTES THAT RESULT IN THE CANCELLATION OF THE CREDIT AGREEMENT

- AUCTION OF COLLATERAL GOODS PERSPECTIVE OF ISLAMIC ECONOMIC LAW
- Review of the Implementation of Auctions on Mortgage Collateral in Bad Credit Cases (Study Decision Number 86/PDT/2015/PT.MDN)
- The Validity of a Power of Attorney Imposing Mortgage Rights Created on Collateral That is Still Subject to Mortgage Rights for Other Creditors
- Juridical Review of Notary/PPAT Covernotes Regarding Installation of Bank Collateral Mortgage Rights
- Analysis of Credit Provision to Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises Without Collateral at PT. Bank Danamon Tbk
- Review of the Implementation of Lending and Borrowing Agreements Without Additional Collateral in Cooperatives
- NEGOTIATION PROCESS IN APPLYING FOR BANK CREDIT (CASE STUDY IN THE CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL SECTION OF PT BANK NUSANTARA PARAHYANGAN TBK KCU SU DIRMAN BANDUNG)
- GENERALIZED MEAN DISTANCE-BASED K-NEAREST NEIGHBOR CLASSIFIER (GMDKNN) METHOD FOR CREDIT SCORING ANALYSIS OF PROSPECTIVE UNCOLLECTIVE CREDIT DEBTORS (KTA)
- ANALYSIS OF FACTORS THAT INFLUENCE THE LEVEL OF APPROVAL OF SUBSEQUENT SHARIA FINANCING FACILITIES FOR COLLATERAL-NOT (PTA) FINANCING PRODUCTS (Case Study of PT. Bank ABC Syariah in Indonesia)
- JURIDICAL REVIEW OF COLLATERAL TAKEAWAY (AYDA) BY BANK
- IMPLEMENTATION OF LEGAL PROTECTION FOR CREDITORS IN PROVIDING WORKING CAPITAL CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL
- ASPECTS OF COLLATERAL BANK PROVIDING PEOPLE'S CREDIT
- SETTLEMENT OF BAD CREDIT WITH FOREIGNED COLLATERAL (AYDA) AS A CREDITOR PROTECTION MEASURE IN REGIONAL COMPANY BPR BANK KLATEN
- DEBTOR DEFAULT IN HOME COLLATERAL CREDIT AGREEMENT AT PT. STATE SAVINGS BANK (PERSERO) Tbk PONTIANAK BRANCH
- EXECUTION RIGHTS OF SEPARATIST CREDITORS AGAINST COLLATERAL OBJECTS IN BANKRUPTCY
- JUDGE'S CONSIDERATIONS IN DECIDING CASES CONCERNING THE LEGAL STATUS OF COLLATERAL OBJECTS OWNED BY THIRD PARTIES IN DEBTOR'S BANKRUPTCY (Case Study of Supreme Court Decision Number 16 PK/Pdt.Sus-Pailit 2015 Jo. Number 157 k/Pdt.Sus-Pailit/2014 Jo. Number 18/Plw.Pailit/2013/PN-
- SETTLEMENT OF BAD CREDIT THROUGH THE PURCHASE AND SALE OF COLLATERAL BY THE BANK ACCORDING TO LAW NO. 10 OF 1998 CONCERNING BANKING
- CREDITORS AND DEBTORS WITH LEGAL PROTECTION RIGHTS IN UNCOLLATERAL CREDIT AGREEMENTS
- Analysis of the assessment of collateral aspects in murabahah financing
- Juridical Study of Onrechtmatigedaad as a Factor for Auction Cancellation in Collateral Objects
- IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POWER TO SELL CREDIT COLLATERAL AT PT. INDONESIAN PEOPLE'S BANK (PERSERO) TBK UNIT SUDIRMAN PEKANBARU

- THE ROLE OF INTERNAL AUDIT AND INTERNAL CONTROL SYSTEM FOR APPLICATION OF UNCOLLATERED CREDIT IN BANKING COMPANIES IN INDONESIA
- Legal Protection for Debtors (Customers) in Unsecured Credit Agreements Judging from Law Number 8 of 1999 concerning Consumer Protection
- STUDY ON THE POSITION OF COLLATERAL IN MUDHARABAH FINANCING AGREEMENTS IN SHARIA BANK
- LEGAL REVIEW OF SETTLEMENT OF BAD CREDITS THROUGH SALE OF COLLATERAL BY BANK BASED ON LAW NUMBER 10 OF 1998
- Standard Clauses in Unsecured Credit Agreements at Bank Permata; Study of the Implementation of Law Number 8 of 1999 concerning Consumer Protection
- Legal Protection for Creditors in Micro People's Business Credit (KUR) Agreements Without Collateral
- JURIDICAL REVIEW OF CO-OWNED LAND AS COLLATERAL IN BANK CREDIT AGREEMENTS BASED ON LAW NUMBER 4 OF 1996
- IMPLEMENTATION OF COLLATERAL AUCTIONS FOR PROBLEM FINANCING IN MURABAHAH AGREEMENTS
- LEGAL RESPONSIBILITY OF BANK BRI SYARIAH DUE TO THE LOSS OF DEBTORS' COLLATERAL IN THE CITY OF BALIKPAPAN
- Legal Protection of Debtor Collateral Data from a Banking Secrecy Perspective
- A REVIEW OF THE CONCEPT OF COLLATERAL IN FINANCING MUDHARABAH AGREEMENTS IN SHARIA BANK
- LEGAL CONSTRUCTION OF TEACHER CERTIFICATES AS COLLATERAL FOR FINANCING REVIEWED FROM GUARANTEE LAW IN INDONESIA (Study at BPR Syariah Dana Mulia Surakarta)
- EXECUTION OF ADDITIONAL GUARANTEES IN THE CREDIT AGREEMENT DECISION LETTER OF APPOINTMENT TO THE POSITION OF THE STATE CIVIL APPARATUS AS BANK COLLATERAL
- EXPLORATION OF THE C4.5 ALGORITHM AND FORWARD FEATURE SELECTION TO DETERMINE GOOD DEBTORS AND PROBLEM DEBTORS IN UNCOLLATERAL CREDIT (KTA) PRODUCTS
- POTENTIAL FOR SOCIAL CAPITAL IN REGIONAL COMMUNITIES POST DISASTER IN PONOROGO DISTRICT (INITIATION OF AN ALTERNATIVE COLLATERAL MODEL BASED ON SOCIAL CAPITAL)
- ANALYSIS OF MUSYARAKAH AGREEMENTS IN GOLD-BASED BUSINESS CAPITAL FINANCING FROM AN ISLAMIC LEGAL PERSPECTIVE (Case Study at PT BPRS Mandiri Mitra Sukses Gresik)
- COPYRIGHT COLLATERAL APPRAISAL IN BANKING IN INDONESIA
- THE INFLUENCE OF NON PERFORMING LOANS (NPL) ON DISTRIBUTION OF HOME COLLATERAL CREDIT (KAR) AT PT. STATE SAVINGS BANK (PERSERO) TBK
- RISK MANAGEMENT OF PROVIDING CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL TO REDUCE CREDIT RISK AT PT. BANK NEGARA INDONESIA (PERSERO) TBK FATMAWATI MAIN BRANCH OFFICE
- RECOVERY OF REGIONAL ASSETS USED AS COLLATERAL BY THIRD PARTIES IN COOPERATION AGREEMENTS WITH BUMD

- THE INFLUENCE OF MOTOR VEHICLE OWNERS' BOOKED COLLATERAL PAYMENTS (BPKB) ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL AND MEDIUM ENTERPRISES (UKM)
- LEGAL ASPECTS OF PRUDENTIAL PRINCIPLES AND THE FIVE C OF CREDIT ANALYSIS IN PROVIDING CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL BY BANK AND THEIR LEGAL CONSEQUENCES
- THE INFLUENCE OF MICRO CREDIT, CREDIT COLLATERAL AND CAPACITY BUILDING ON THE FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF MICRO ENTERPRISES (Study of Members of the Financial Management Unit - BKM Kendari City)
- ANALYSIS OF BRAND RIGHTS AS COLLATERAL IN PROVIDING BANK CREDIT
- TRANSFER OF MONITORING RIGHTS UNDER HANDS ON THE COLLATERAL LAND OF PT. INDONESIAN PEOPLE'S BANK BABANGSINTONG TANAH PUTIH DISTRICT, ROKAN HILIR RIAU DISTRICT
- EFFECTIVENESS OF PROBLEM CREDIT SETTLEMENT AT BANK JATIM BY SALES OF COLLATERAL UNDER HANDS
- Legal Protection for Debtors (Customers) in Credit Agreements Without Collateral Reviewed from Law Number 8 of 1999 concerning Consumer Protection
- Legality of Rural Banks in Carrying Out Collateral Procedures that are Taken Over on Mortgage Rights Objects
- Collateral Aspects as Legal Protection for Banks as Online Credit Service Providers
- Application of Cross Default and Cross Collateral Principles in Credit Agreements with Land Rights as Collateral (Study of PT. Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk.)
- Copyright as Bank Credit Collateral
- FOREIGNED COLLATERAL: A MECHANISM IN SETTLEMENT OF BAD CREDITS
- Legal Protection for Creditors in Providing Credit Without Collateral
- THE INFLUENCE OF LOAN INTEREST RATES, COMPANY AGE AND COLLATERAL ON CREDIT REQUEST DECISIONS (Case Study of Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises in Solo Raya)
- Independence in Determining the Amount of Collateral Value in Credit Agreements Made by Appraisal Bank
- Handling and Efforts by the Bank for Problematic MSME Credit Debtors by Providing Additional Collateral to PT BPR Sinar Kuta
- Settlement of Credit Guaranteed by Mortgage with Ayda (Foreclosed Collateral) of the Bank through Auction
- PRINCIPLES OF PRECAUTION IN DISTRIBUTION OF CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL DISTRIBUTED BY PT BANK MANDIRI, Tbk
- ANALYSIS OF COLLATERAL INCLUSION IN MUDARABAH FINANCING:: Perspective of DSN-MUI Fatwa No. 07/DSN-MUI/IV/2000 and Law no. 21 of 2008 concerning Sharia Banking
- Legal Protection for Lenders in Lending and Borrowing Money Without Collateral Based on Information Technology

- IMPLEMENTATION OF EXECUTION PARATE ON OBJECTS OF MONITORED RIGHTS COLLATERAL AT PT. BANK KALBAR PUTUSSIBAU BRANCH
- The influence of corporate governance, audit quality, and conservatism on loan collateral requirements
- Settlement of Unsecured Credit Disputes in Patrang Village, Patrang District, Jember Regency
- LEGAL PROTECTION OF DEBTORS IN LOANS WITHOUT COLLATERAL FUNDS DURING THE COVID-19 PANDEMIC
- IMPROVING COMMUNITY UNDERSTANDING OF BANKING COLLATERAL IN SUNGAI KUNING VILLAGE, RAMBAH SAMO DISTRICT, ROKAN HULU DISTRICT
- SETTING OF CREDIT POLICY WITHOUT COLLATERAL IN INDONESIA
- MECHANISM FOR COLLATERAL TAKEOVER BY PEOPLE'S CREDIT BANK WHICH HAS POSTED MONITORY RIGHTS RELATED TO SETTLEMENT OF BAD CREDIT
- FUNCTION OF DOCUMENT CONTROL AND BINDING OF COLLATERAL AS SECURITY IN PROVIDING BANKING CREDIT
- Responsibilities of the Debtor in the Unsecured Credit Agreement (KTA) at the Kuta Imba Multipurpose Cooperative (KSU) Badung Regency
- ARRANGEMENTS FOR SETTLEMENT OF BAD CREDIT IN UNCOLLATERAL CREDIT AGREEMENTS BASED ON BANKING LAW
- THE INFLUENCE OF SALES PROMOTION AND PERSONAL SELLING ON UNCOLLATERAL CREDIT DECISION MAKING
- DELIVERY OF COLLATERAL OBJECTS BY SALE AND PURCHASE AGREEMENT ACCORDING TO INDONESIAN POSITIVE LAW
- THE FUNCTION OF COLLATERAL IN SHARIA BANKING FROM THE PERSPECTIVE OF POSITIVE LAW AND ISLAMIC LAW (The Function of Collateral in Sharia Banking from The Perspective of Positive Law and Islamic Law)
- JURIDICAL ANALYSIS OF PNS SK COLLATERAL REVIEW FROM THE DSN FATWA CONCERNING RAHN TASJILY
- REVIEW OF THE LAW REGARDING CREDIT OFFERS WITHOUT COLLATERAL (KTA) VIA SHORT MESSAGE SERVICE (SMS)
- IMPLEMENTATION OF CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL AT PT. PEOPLE'S CREDIT BANK (BPR) PADMA DENPASAR
- Assessment of Murabahah Financing Collateral Aspects (Case Study of RFO BSI Tbk, Medan)
- Juridical Consequences of Foreclosed Collateral on the Dissolution of the Agreement
- Application of the Corruption Crime Law to the Crime of Manipulating Collateral Data in Credit Applications at BUMD Banks
- Characteristics of Land Redistribution Activities in West Pasaman Regency based on Use for Collateral
- JURIDICAL STUDY FOR THE EXECUTION OF CREDIT RIGHTS FOR LIMITED COMPANY CREDIT WITH PERSONAL ASSETS AS COLLATERAL (Case study of Decision on Case Number 348/Pdt.G/2020/PN Sby)
- EFFORTS TO SOLVE BAD CREDIT WITHOUT COLLATERAL IN PEER TO PEER LENDING

- Practice of Implementing the Principle of Trust (Fiduciary Principle) in Providing Unsecured Credit (KTA) to Company Employees
- Application of Finite State Automata in the Process of Applying for Unsecured Financing (Mitraguna) at PT Bank Syariah Indonesia
- Legal Protection for Customers and Banks in Providing Unsecured Credit if Credit Problems Occur Post Covid 19 Pandemic
- ANALYSIS OF DETERMINING COLLATERAL ELIGIBILITY IN DISTRIBUTION OF MURABAHAH FINANCING REVIEWED FROM SHARIA BANK RISK MANAGEMENT (Case Study at BPRS Rahma Syariah Kediri)
- Legal Consequences of Credit Agreements with Uncontrolled Credit Collateral (Study of Supreme Court Decision Number 2221 K/Pdt/2020)
- JOURNAL TITLE (COLLATERAL)
- Selling Authorization Legal Agreement Status Will Be Weighed Against Collateral Mortgage (Case Study PT. Bank Tabungan Negara (Persero) Tbk.)
- Idea of Collateral and Guarantor in Islamic Bank Financing
- APPLICATION OF THE CONCEPT OF CHARACTER, CAPACITY, CAPITAL, COLLATERAL, CONDITION (5C) IN THE MICRO BUSINESS CREDIT PROVIDING SYSTEM AT PT BANK MANDIRI (PERSERO) TBK UNIT MANDIRI MITRA BUSINESS BALIKPAPAN UNIVERSITY OF BALIKPAPAN
- Collateral As Expired Solution a Risk of Mudharabah Financing (Case Study of Bank Syariah Mandiri Bank KCP. Ponorogo)
- THE EFFECT OF CUSTOMERS' INCOME, BUSINESS CAPITAL, MARGIN AND COLLATERAL VALUE ON MURABAHAH FINANCING DEMAND AT BANK BNI SYARIAH MIKRO BANTU PRAYA BRANCH OFFICE.
- PATENTS AS FIDUCIARY COLLATERAL IN BANK CREDIT
- The Influence of the Principles of Character, Capacity, Capital, Collateral, Condition of Economy on PT Credit Decision Making. Bank Negara Indonesia KCU Cibinong 2020
- Application of Cross Default and Cross Collateral Principles in Credit Agreements with Land Rights as Collateral (Study of PT. Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk.)
- Legality of Execution of Collateral Based on Electronic Mortgage Certificate in Bank Credit Agreement
- THE INFLUENCE OF CHARACTER, CAPACITY, CAPITAL, CONDITION AND COLLATERAL ON THE DECISION TO PROVIDE FINANCING AT PT BANK SUMUT SHARIAH BUSINESS DIVISION
- Factors Affecting Collateral Valuation Performance During the Covid-19 Pandemic: An Evidence from Islamic Bank in Indonesia
- ANALYSIS OF COLLATERAL AUCTION IMPLEMENTATION IN SHARIA BANK FROM SHARIA ECONOMIC PERSPECTIVE
- JOURNAL TITLE (GUARANTEE)
- DEVELOPMENT OF THE HEDONIC MODEL AS A TOOL FOR DETERMINING THE VALUE OF LAND COLLATERAL FOR BANK CREDIT
- UTILIZATION OF FIDUCIARY GUARANTEES IN PEOPLE'S CREDIT BANKS
- IMPLICATIONS OF LAW NO. 42 OF 1999 CONCERNING FIDUCIARY GUARANTEES FOR LEGAL PROTECTION OF BANK AS CREDITORS

- Implementation of Marine Ship Mortgage Guarantee Between PT. Bank Nasional Indonesia Jambi Branch with PT. Beautiful Sabak in East Tanjung Jabung
- Employee Appointment Decree as Credit Guarantee at the Bank
- ANALYSIS OF DETERMINATION No: 01/Pen.Pdt.G/Eks/HT/2010/PN-Pms Concerning EXECUTION OF GUARANTEED GOODS BY BANK IN SETTLEMENT OF CREDIT PROBLEMS
- Legal Protection for Guarantor in Individual Guarantee Agreement (Borgtocht) at PT Bank Artha Graha Internasional Tbk Samarinda Branch
- JURIDICAL REVIEW OF THE LEGAL EFFECTS OF UNREGISTERED FIDUCIARY GUARANTEES ON CREDIT LORNING IN BANK
- LEGAL ASPECTS OF BANK GUARANTEE AGENCY LEGAL ASPECTS OF BANK GUARANTEE SECURITY AGENCY
- BAD CREDIT PROBLEMATICS WITH COLLATERALS THAT ARE NOT REGISTERED IN FIDUCIA FORM AT SAMARINDA PEOPLE'S CREDIT BANK
- EFFORTS TO HANDLE MASS SELF-OWNED CREDIT CREDITS (SMS) WITH GUARANTEES OF MONITORING RIGHTS IN REGIONAL COMPANIES OF LAMONGAN PEOPLE'S CREDIT BANK
- THE SUITABILITY OF IMPLEMENTING THE AUCTION OF RAHN'S GUARANTEED GOODS IS PROBLEM BASED ON THE FATWA OF THE NATIONAL SYARIAH COUNCIL NUMBER 25/DSN-MUI/III/2002 (Study at PT. Bank BRI Syariah Malang City Branch)
- IMPLEMENTATION OF LEGAL PROTECTION AGAINST BANK IN THE CASE OF THE TRANSFER OF THE OBJECT OF FIDUCIARY SECURITY BY THE DEBTOR WITHOUT THE CONSENT OF THE CREDITOR (Study at PT. Bank Negara Indonesia (PERSERO) Tbk. Pamekasan Regency)
- JURIDICAL REVIEW OF PROVIDING BANK CREDIT WITH PERSONAL GUARANTEE (Study at BRI Bank, Willem Iskandar KCP Branch)
- DEPOSIT PAYMENT GUARANTEE IN THE BANK GUARANTEE AGREEMENT AT PT. BANK VICTORIA SYARIAH JAKARTA
- IMPLEMENTATION OF CREDIT AGREEMENT WITH GUARANTEE OF EDUCATIONAL CERTIFICATE AT PT. BUMI PENDAWA RAHARJA CIANJUR PEOPLE'S CREDIT BANK
- CREDIT AGREEMENT WITH GUARANTEE OF MORTGAGE RIGHTS WHERE THE DEBTOR ENTERED INTO A MARRIAGE AGREEMENT (Case Study of Losses at PT. Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero), Tbk, Semarang Pattimura Branch)
- Power of Attorney Imposing Fiduciary Guarantees on Credit Agreements at PT. Gunung Simping Artha Sokaraja People's Credit Bank
- LEGAL CONSEQUENCES FOR FIDUCIARY CREDITORS IF THE OBJECT OF THE FIDUCIARY SECURITY IS DESTROYED (Study at PT. Bank BNI Syariah, Semarang Branch)
- THE EFFECTIVENESS OF A CREDIT AGREEMENT AS A BINDING OF CREDIT GUARANTEE IN PEOPLE'S CREDIT BANK KRANJI KRIDA SEJAHTERA BEKASI CITY
- LEGAL CONSEQUENCES OF DEBTOR DEFECTS IN CREDIT AGREEMENTS WITH CESSIE GUARANTEES AT PT. BANK MANDIRI (PERSERO) TBK. COMMERCIAL BANKING CENTER DENPASAR BRANCH

- LEGAL PROTECTION FOR CREDITORS IN CREDIT AGREEMENTS WITH GUARANTEE OF MORTGAGE RIGHTS STUDY AT BANK BNI WEST GATSU BRANCH
- SUSPENSION OF EXECUTION OF CREDIT GUARANTEE RIGHTS OBJECTS IN BANK FROM BANKRUPTCY COMPANIES
- CREDIT AGREEMENT WITH FIDUCIARY GUARANTEE IN THE FORM OF STOCK OF MERCHANDISE (Livestock) (Study at PT Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Pati Small Credit Center)
- Implementation of Credit Provision with Warehouse Receipt Guarantee (Bank Rakyat Indonesia Pekalongan Branch)
- BENEFITS OF FIDUCIARY GUARANTEES IN IMPLEMENTING BANK CREDIT AGREEMENTS
- Analysis of PT Claim Payments. Jamsostek (Persero) for Bank Lampung Employees in Bandar Lampung Based on Law Number 3 of 1992 concerning Workers' Social Security
- Credit Facilities Without Material Collateral Rights (Study of Providing Credit Cards at Bank Negara Indonesia (Persero) Tbk/Research Results)
- Implementation of Heirs' Responsibilities for Heirs' Debts on Credit Facilities â€ Capital Solutions â€ Without Collateral (Study at Bank Danamon Savings and Loans Capital Solutions Unit Jombang).
- BANK'S EFFORTS IN HANDLING PROBLEM COMMUNITY BUSINESS CREDIT DEBTORS THROUGH FULFILLING THE OBLIGATION TO PROVIDE ADDITIONAL GUARANTEE (Case study at Bank Rakyat Indonesia Malang Sutoyo Branch)
- IMPLEMENTATION OF THE BANK'S PRUDENTIAL PRINCIPLES IN PROVIDING CREDIT WITH A GUARANTEE OF WAREHOUSE RECEIPT FOR GRAIN (Study at PT. Bank Jatim, Mojokerto Branch)
- Analysis of the Influence of Trust, Guarantee of Security, and Accessibility on Saving Interest of Bank Danamon Customers in Surabaya
- SETTLEMENT OF BAD CREDIT WITH FICTIONAL GUARANTEES IN THE FORM OF FICTITIOUS RECEIVABLES. (Study at PT. Bank Rakyat Indonesia (PERSERO) Tbk. Tulungagung Branch).
- FUNCTION OF GUARANTEE IN MUSYARAKAH FINANCING (STUDY AT PT BANK KALSEL SYARIAH BANJARMASIN BRANCH)
- THE EXISTENCE OF PAYMENT AS A SECURITY INSTITUTION AMIDST THE PROSPERITY OF PEOPLE'S CREDIT BANK (BPR) AND SAVINGS AND LOAN COOPERATIONS (KSP) TODAY
- TERM DEPOSITS AS COLLATERAL PAYMENT ON THE BANK IN A CREDIT AGREEMENT
- THE POWER OF EXECUTION OF MORTGAGE RIGHTS AS GUARANTEE TO RETURN PROBLEM FINANCING DEBT IN THE PRACTICES OF PT. BANK MUAMALAT INDONESIA, TBK MEDAN BRANCH
- THE EXECUTION OF FIDUCIARY GUARANTEES AT BANK SYARIAH MANDIRI MALANG CITY REVIEWED FROM DSN MUI FATWA NUMBER 68 OF 2008
- THE RIGHT TO PENSION AS DEBT COLLECTION AT THE SAMARINDA BRANCH OF THE ROCKY BANK OF INDONESIA
- Implementation of Fiduciary Guarantees for Murabahah Financing at BPR (People's Financing Bank) Syariah Mandiri Mitra Sukses Gresik

- DEBTOR'S RESPONSIBILITY FOR DESTROYED FIDUCIARY SECURITY OBJECTS IN THE BANK CREDIT AGREEMENT
- LEGAL STUDY ON THE POSITION OF BANK AS HOLDERS OF MORTGAGE RIGHTS ON THE EXPIRATION OF THE CERTIFICATE OF BUILDING USE RIGHTS OVER MANAGEMENT RIGHTS (HPL) WHICH ARE THE OBJECT OF GUARANTEE (STUDY: PT BANK INTERNASIONAL INDONESIA, TBK BRANCH MEDAN DIPONEGORO)
- JURIDICAL ANALYSIS OF FACTORS INHIBITING THE EXECUTION OF FIDUCIARY GUARANTEES IN PROTECTING CREDITORS (STUDY ON PT. BANK M ANDIRI (PERSERO), Tbk BALAIKOTA MEDAN)
- THE INFLUENCE OF THE AMOUNT OF GUARANTEE ON CREDIT PROVIDING AT BANK BPR EAST JAVA (BANK UMKM EAST JAVA) MAGETAN BRANCH IN 2012/2013
- Securing the Provision of Bank Credit with Guarantee of Building Use Rights
- IMPLEMENTATION OF INDIVIDUAL GUARANTEED CREDIT AGREEMENTS RELATED TO DEFENDANT DEBTORS AT PEOPLE'S CREDIT BANK
- DEBTOR'S RESPONSIBILITY FOR THE DESTRUCTION OF FIDUCIARY SECURITY OBJECTS IN THE BANK CREDIT AGREEMENT
- HANDLING OF MULTI-PURPOSE CREDIT IS PROBLEM WITH THE GUARANTEE OF THE DECISION LETTER FOR THE APPOINTMENT OF CIVIL SERVANTS BY PT BANK JATIM TBK. MALANG BRANCH
- THE POSITION OF THE DECISION LETTER ON THE APPOINTMENT OF MEMBERS OF THE REGIONAL REPRESENTATIVE COUNCIL IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE CREDIT AGREEMENT AS THE OBJECT OF GUARANTEE AT PT. BANK RIAU KEPRI MAIN BRANCH PEKANBARU
- LEGAL ACTIONS OF BANK AS FINANCERS OF FIDUCIARY GUARANTEES DURING BAD CREDITS
- THE EXISTENCE AND EXECUTORIAL POWER OF A CERTIFICATE OF MONITORY RIGHTS ON OWNERSHIP RIGHTS TO A FLAT AS A DEBT SECURITY IN A CREDIT AGREEMENT IN A BANK
- PROVIDING BANK CREDIT FACILITIES WITH TERM DEPOSIT GUARANTEES
- ANALYSIS REGARDING THE PROVISION OF WORKING CAPITAL CREDIT FACILITIES BY BANK THROUGH THE "TAKE OVER" MECHANISM (Study of Procedures and Guarantees at Private Banks in Medan)
- JURIDICAL REVIEW OF THE ACTIONS OF THE DEBTOR WHO REFUSED THE DISMISSAL OF THE COLLATERAL ITEMS EXECUTED BY THE BANK
- JURIDICAL REVIEW OF THE POSITION OF OBJECTS OF GUARANTEE RIGHTS TO BANKS RELATED TO CORRUPTION CASES
- BANK'S POSITION AS HOLDER OF OBJECTS OF OBJECTS OF OBJECTS
- LEGAL EFFECTIVENESS OF PROVIDING CREDIT FACILITIES BY BANK WITH RATED COLLEGE RIGHTS GUARANTEE (STUDY OF STATE SAVINGS BANK MALANG BRANCH)
- EXECUTION OF GUARANTEED GOODS THAT ARE BOUND BY FIDUCIARY IN THE BANK

- IMPLEMENTATION OF CREDIT PROVIDING WITH GUARANTEE OF COLLEGE RIGHTS TO DEBTORS PT. CENTRAL DKI JAKARTA BANK
- ANALYSIS OF DEBT AND RECOVERY AGREEMENTS WITH PLEDGE OF SHARES IN THE CASE OF DEUTSCHE BANK AKTIENGESELLSCHAFT VS BECKETT, PTE.LTD.
- ANALYSIS OF CREDIT AGREEMENTS WITH THE OBJECT OF GUARANTEE IN THE FORM OF A WIDOW/WIDOW'S PENSION DECISION AT THE NATIONAL RETIREMENT SAVINGS BANK DENPASAR
- BANK CREDIT AGREEMENT GUARANTEE IN DISTRIBUTION OF FUNDS TO THE COMMUNITY
- BANK FACTORS IN PROVIDING CREDIT LOANS WITH COMMODITY GOODS GUARANTEE
- LEGAL EFFECTS OF THE FIDUCIARY GUARANTEE DEED THAT WAS NOT REGISTERED AT PEKANBARU TUAH NEGERI MANDIRI PEKANBARU PEOPLE'S CREDIT BANK (BPR)
- SETTLEMENT OF CREDIT PROBLEMS THROUGH GUARANTEE OFFSET AT BANK BUKOPIN BANDA ACEH BRANCH
- DISPUTE RESOLUTION OF FULFILLMENT OF OLD AGE GUARANTEES FOR PT EMPLOYEES. BANK BRI PERSERO AT BANDAR LAMPUNG BRANCH (Analysis of Decision No. 7/Pdt.Sus-PHI/2015/PN.Tjk)
- EXECUTION OF MONEY RIGHTS GUARANTEES AS AN EFFORT TO SOLVE FINANCING PROBLEMS (Study at PT Bank Muamalat Indonesia Lampung Branch)
- Protection Efforts for the Bank Due to the Transfer of Fiduciary Security Objects which are Transferred by the Customer Without Prior Approval from the Bank (Case Study at PT. Bank Negara Indonesia, Malang).
- LEGAL PROTECTION OF BANK ON CREDIT WITH GUARANTEE OF DECISION LETTER OF APPOINTMENT OF CIVIL SERVANTS IN THE EVENT OF BAD CREDIT (Study at Bank Jatim Malang Branch)
- EFFORTS OF THE CREDITOR (BANK) TO OBTAIN GUARANTEES FOR PAYMENT OF THE CREDIT AGREEMENT DUE TO THE OBJECT OF THE COLLATERAL CHANGING HANDS DUE TO A COURT RULING (Case Study at Bank Bukopin, Manado Branch, North Sulawesi)
- BANK LEGAL CONSIDERATIONS IN ACCEPTING EIGENDOM VERPONDING CERTIFICATES AS GUARANTEE FOR MICRO KUR (STUDY AT PT. BANKRAKYAT INDONESIA UNIT PUCANG ANOM SURABAYA)
- EXECUTION OF COLLATERAL OBJECTS WHICH ARE BURDENED BY MORTGAGE RIGHTS THROUGH UNDER HAND SALES (STUDY AT PT. BANK RAKYAT INDONESIA KAWI-MALANG BRANCH OFFICE)
- EFFORTS TO HANDLE PROBLEM CREDIT BY GUARANTEEING A STATE CIVIL APPARATUS DECISION IN THE EVENT THE DEBTOR DIES (Case Study of PT. Bank Rakyat Indonesia, Tulungagung Branch, Tugurante Ngunut Unit)
- IMPLEMENTATION OF PT. CREDIT AGREEMENT. BANK RAKYAT INDONESIA (PERSERO) BUKIT AGUNG UNIT PANGKALAN KERINCI BRANCH WITH GUARANTEE OF COMPENSATION LETTER (SKGR)
- IMPLEMENTATION OF CREDIT PROVIDING WITH GUARANTEE OF MOBILE RIGHTS TO PT. PERMATA BANK Tbk PEKANBARU BRANCH BASED ON LAW NUMBER 4 OF 1996 CONCERNING MONITORING RIGHTS TO LAND AND OBJECTS RELATING TO LAND

- GUARANTEE FUNCTION REGARDING CREDIT PROVIDING BY THE BANK ACCORDING TO LAW NUMBER 10 OF 1998
- IMPLEMENTATION OF ONLINE REGISTRATION OF FIDUCIARY GUARANTEES BY FIDUCIARY CREDITORS (CASE STUDY AT PEOPLE'S CREDIT BANK SEMARANG CITY)
- JURIDICAL ANALYSIS OF MUDHARABAH FINANCING WITH TREASURE GUARANTEES IN SHARIA BANKING ACCORDING TO ISLAMIC LAW (STUDY AT MANDIRI BANK LHOKSEUMAWE CITY BRANCH)
- DEBTOR'S RESPONSIBILITY FOR THE DESTRUCTION OF FIDUCIARY SECURITY OBJECTS IN THE BANK CREDIT AGREEMENT
- JURIDICAL ANALYSIS OF CREDITORS' RESPONSIBILITY DURING THE SUPERVISION PERIOD BEFORE THE AUCTION EXPERIENCED THE LOSS OF PART OF THE PROPERTY OF THE GUARANTEED ITEMS (STUDY AT PT. BANK SUMUT BANTU MELATI BRANCH)
- APPLICATION OF THE PRINCIPLE OF PACTA SUNT SERVANDA IN THE UNGUARANTEED CREDIT AGREEMENT AT BANK MANDIRI BRANCH BRANCH CITRA GARDEN MEDAN
- DEPOSITS AS SECURITY FOR CREDIT AT BANK MANDIRI SANUR BRANCH
- BANK MUAMALAT INDONESIA'S TREATMENT TOWARDS THE PAYMENT OF CLAIMS FOR THE DESTRUCTION OF THE DEBTOR'S GUARANTEED GOODS BY THE INSURANCE PARTY
- EFFECTIVENESS OF IMPLEMENTING ELECTRONIC FIDUCIARY REGISTRATION ON SHARIA BANK FINANCING (Study at Artha Amanah Ummat Sharia People's Financing Bank, Semarang Regency)
- BANK CONSIDERATIONS IN PROVIDING MICRO CREDIT WITH GUARANTEE OF LAND RIGHTS WITHOUT MONEY RIGHTS (Study of PT. Bank Rakyat Indonesia Sulfat Unit, Malang)
- LEGAL PROTECTION FOR CREDITORS IN THE EXECUTION OF GUARANTEES FOR DEFENDANT DEBTORS' RIGHTS AT PT. BANK MANDIRI (PERSERO) TBK PONTIANAK
- GUARANTEE OF LEGAL PROTECTION FOR CREDITORS HOLDING SHARE PLEDGES IN NATIONAL COMMERCIAL BANKS IN INDONESIA
- TRANSFER OF THE OBJECT OF FIDUCIARY SECURITY BY THE DEBTOR WITHOUT THE CREDITOR'S CONSENT IN THE BANK CREDIT AGREEMENT
- JURIDICAL ASPECTS OF PROVIDING MICRO PEOPLE'S BUSINESS CREDIT (KUR) WITHOUT COLLATERAL FOR SMALL BUSINESSES THROUGH THE STATE BANK OF INDONESIA (BNI) BNI SMALL CREDIT CENTER (SKC) BRANCH MT. HARYONO SEMARANG
- PROVIDING CREDIT WITH LAND GUARANTEE CERTIFICATE LETTER (SK) OF CAMAT AT PT. INDONESIAN PEOPLE'S BANK (PERSERO) Tbk. MEDAN SISINGAMANGARAJA BRANCH
- EFFORTS TO SOLVE BAD CREDIT ON MOBILE GUARANTEES (Study at PT Bank Sumut Stabat Branch)
- JURIDICAL REVIEW REGARDING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF CREDIT AGREEMENTS WITH THE GUARANTEE OF A LICENSE TO USE THE BUSINESS PLACE BETWEEN THE DEBTOR AND THE CREDITOR (Study at Bank Danamon Medan Branch)

- IMPLEMENTATION OF MITRA-25 AND MITRA-02 CREDIT PROVIDING THROUGH UNGUARANTEED CREDIT AGREEMENTS (Study at the Central Java Regional Development Bank, Purbalingga Branch Office)
- LEGAL REVIEW OF FIDUCIARY GUARANTEES THAT ARE NOT REGISTERED IN NON BANK CREDIT LENDING
- ALTERNATIVE MODEL FOR RESOLUTION OF FIDUCIARY GUARANTEE DISPUTES IN WHICH THE OBJECT OF THE WARRANTY IS SOLD BY THE DEBTOR BASED ON PRINCIPLES OF JUSTICE IN PEOPLE'S CREDIT BANKS (Case Study at BPR in Malang)
- JURIDICAL ANALYSIS OF THE USE OF CESSIE INSTITUTIONS IN KIOSK GUARANTEE CREDIT AGREEMENTS AT PT. BANK DANAMON INDONESIA
- LEGAL PROTECTION TOWARDS CREDITORS IN PROVIDING CREDIT WITH A PURCHASING ORDER GUARANTEE IF THE DEBTOR IS IN DEFAULT (STUDY OF THE CREDIT AGREEMENT OF PT. BANK MANDIRI AND PT. ERA BANGUN JAYA)
- LEGAL PROTECTION AGAINST WINNING TICKETS WHO ARE IN GOOD FAITH FOR CLAIMS AGAINST DEBTORS PROVIDING MORTGAGE RIGHTS WHICH HAVE BEEN AUCTIONED BY THE BANK (STUDY OF SUPREME COURT RULING NO. 3564.K/PDT/2015)
- JURIDICAL ANALYSIS OF THE AUCTION OF GUARANTEED GOODS WHICH HAS NOT BEEN ASSIGNED (STUDY AT PT. BANK MANDIRI (PERSERO) TBK)
- PROVIDING PRODUCTIVE CREDIT ON MOTOR VEHICLES WITH A FIDUCIA GUARANTEE (CASE STUDY AT PT BANK TABUNGAN PENSIONAN NASIONAL Tbk)
- SETTLEMENT OF CREDIT PROBLEMS BY GUARANTEE OF CIVIL SERVANT DECISION LETTER FOR DISCHARGED CIVIL SERVANTS (STUDY AT PT. BANK ACEH SABANG CITY BRANCH)
- PROVIDING BANK CREDIT WITH A GUARANTEE OF BUILDING USE RIGHTS WHICH TERM HAS EXPIRED WHILE THE CREDIT AGREEMENT HAS NOT EXPIRED
- PROCESS OF IMPLEMENTING RIGHTS AND OBLIGATIONS IN INTERNET BANKING AGREEMENTS AND GUARANTEES PROVIDED BY BANK TO CUSTOMERS USING INTERNET BANKING (STUDY AT BNI BANK PADANG BRANCH)
- CREDIT AGREEMENT WITH GUARANTEE OF OWNERSHIP OF LAND AND BUILDINGS AT BANK TABUNGAN NEGARA MANADO BRANCH ACCORDING TO LAW NO. 4 OF 1996 CONCERNING MONITORING RIGHTS
- Legal Protection for Creditors If the Object of Fiduciary Collateral Turns Out to Be Lost and the Debtor Defaults (Case Study at PT. Bank Perkreditan Rakyat Dinamika Bangun Arta Salatiga)
- LEGAL PROTECTION FOR BANK TO PREVENT LOSSES DUE TO PROBLEMS OF CREDIT WITH A PERSONAL GUARANTEE
- IMPLEMENTATION OF LEGAL PROTECTION FOR CREDITORS DUE TO VIOLATIONS OF COLLATERAL ASSESSMENT IN CREDIT BINDINGS BY PUBLIC APPRAISAL SERVICES (STUDY AT PT. BANK CIMB NIAGA, JEMBER DISTRICT)
- IMPLEMENTATION OF LEGAL PROTECTION FOR CREDITORS IN THE EXECUTION OF FIDUCIARY GUARANTEES FOR SECURITY OBJECTS

IN THE FORM OF RE-GUARANTEED RECEIVABLES (Study at CIMB Niaga Bank, Jember Regency)

- JURIDICAL REVIEW OF THE VALIDITY OF COVER NOTES AS CREDIT GUARANTEE IN BANK
- CUSTOMER'S OBLIGATION NOT TO TRANSFER HANDLES OF WARRANTY GOODS IN THE CREDIT AGREEMENT AT PT. INDONESIAN PEOPLE'S BANK (PERSERO) PONTIANAK BRANCH
- LEGAL PROTECTION AGAINST THIRD PARTIES AS COLLATERAL OWNERS WHEN THE BANK DOES NOT IMPLEMENT THE PRINCIPLES OF PRUDENCE IN CREDIT AGREEMENTS USING COLLATERAL
- LEGAL REVIEW OF THE PROVISION OF CREDIT BY PEOPLE'S CREDIT BANKS (BPR) IN RELATION TO GUARANTEES
- Validity of the Sale and Purchase of Mortgage Objects by Banks which are carried out without going through an Auction Mechanism
- LEGAL CHARACTERISTICS AND IMPLEMENTATION OF BANK GUARANTEES IN CONSTRUCTION SERVICES CONTRACT GUARANTEES
- LEGAL REGULATION OF CREDIT GUARANTEE ASSESSMENT PROCEDURES IN NATIONAL COMMERCIAL BANKS BASED ON LAW NO. 10 OF 1998 CONCERNING BANKING
- LEGAL SANCTIONS AGAINST BANKING INSTITUTIONS THAT DO NOT REGISTER FIDUCIARY GUARANTEES IN CAR OWNERSHIP CREDIT FINANCE PRACTICES (STUDY AT PT. BANK X)
- LEGAL REVIEW OF THE EXECUTION OF GUARANTEES FOR MOVABLE OBJECTS (CARS) DUE TO BAD CREDITS (STUDY AT PT BANK BNI, JL. PEMUDA, MEDAN)
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- APPLICATION OF BANK PRUDENCE PRINCIPLES IN PROVIDING CREDIT WITH GUARANTEE OF WAREHOUSE RECEIPT AT BANK JATENG JEPARA BRANCH OFFICE
- IMPLEMENTATION OF CREDIT AGREEMENTS WITH FIDUCIARY GUARANTEES IN REGIONAL COMPANIES PEOPLE'S CREDIT BANK MARKET BANK SUKOHARJO DISTRICT
- LEGAL PROTECTION OF THE REGISTRATION OF FIDUCIARY GUARANTEES WITH INVENTORY OBJECTS (STOCK OF MERCHANDISE) STUDY AT PT. BANK DANAMON INDONESIA, TBK MEDAN BRANCH
- MECHANISM FOR USE OF TREASURE GUARANTEES (RAHN TASJILY) IN SHARIA BANK FINANCING IN INDONESIA AND MALAYSIA
- IMPLEMENTATION OF RISK MANAGEMENT IN MINIMIZING BANK GUARANTEE PRODUCT CLAIMS IN INSURANCE COMPANIES IN RIAU PROVINCE
- SETTLEMENT OF BAD CREDIT IN A REGULAR INVESTMENT CREDIT AGREEMENT WITH GUARANTEE OF MONITORING RIGHTS AT PT. WEST KALIMANTAN BANK FLAMBOYAN BRANCH

- GUARANTEE OF MONITORING RIGHTS ON MURABAHAH AND MUSYARAKAH FINANCING PRODUCTS AT BANK MUAMALAT INDONESIA
- HANDLING OF DEFENDANT DEBTORS WITH INVENTORY GUARANTEES BASED ON ARTICLE 21 PARAGRAPHS (1) AND (2) JO ARTICLE 29 LAW NUMBER 42 OF 1999 CONCERNING FIDUCIARY GUARANTEES (Study at PD. BPR Regional Bank, Tulungagung Regency, Ng Cash Office)
- THE INFLUENCE OF INCOME INTEREST RATES, CREDIT TERMS AND ESTIMATED CUSTOMER GUARANTEES, ON THE AMOUNT OF CREDIT TAKE-OUTS AT PD BPR BANK KLATEN
- Settlement of Problematic Multipurpose Loans for Dead Debtors with Guarantee of Decree on Appointment of Jombang Regency DPRD Members (Case Study at PD BPR Bank Jombang)
- LEGAL REVIEW REGARDING CURRENT BILYET AS SECURITIES THAT ARE USED AS GUARANTEE FOR THE BANK IN THE EVENT THE CUSTOMER DEFAULTS
- IMPLEMENTATION OF EXECUTION OF OBJECTS OF MONITORY RIGHTS GUARANTEES THROUGH UNDER HANDS SALES (Study at PT Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk Tanjung Karang Branch Office)
- RESPONSIBILITIES OF CREDIT AGREEMENTS WITH THE GUARANTEE OF DECISION LETTER FOR THE APPOINTMENT OF CIVIL SERVANTS (Study at PT. Bank Mandiri (Persero), Tbk. Raden Intan Sub-Branch Office, Bandar Lampung)
- FIDUCIARY GUARANTEE POLICY ON MURABAHAH FINANCING AT BANK SYARIAH MANDIRI PANTU MERDEKA BOGOR BRANCH OFFICE
- THE POSITION OF A FIDUCIARY AS A GUARANTEE FOR A MURABAHAH FINANCING AGREEMENT IN SHARIA BANK: CASE STUDY AT BPRS BHAKTI SUMEKAR SUMENEP
- MARKET STANT AS SECURITY BASED ON THE AGREEMENT CONCERNING GRANTING THE RIGHT TO USE SPACE (STAN) AT BANK CENTRAL ASIA
- AUTHORITY OF THE NOTARY"IN" CREDIT"AGREEMENTS" WITH" FIDUCIARY" GUARANTEES (Study of Rural Banks in Malang Regency)
- RESCUE PROCESS AND RESOLVE FINANCING PROBLEMS USING COLLATERAL ANALYSIS (Case Study at PT Bank Syariah Mandiri Padangsidempuan Branch)
- JURIDICAL ANALYSIS OF CREDIT GRANTING WITH GUARANTEE RETIREMENT DECISION LETTER BY PT. NATIONAL PENSION SAVINGS BANK, Tbk KEDIRI BRANCH, EAST JAVA
- The Influence of Guarantee, Empathy and Reliability on Customer Satisfaction in KPR Bank BJB Bogor Branch
- EFFECTIVENESS OF EXECUTING FIDUCIARY OBJECTS FOR CUSTOMERS WHO DO NOT WANT TO GIVE UP FIDUCIARY OBJECTS VOLUNTARY (STUDY AT PT. BANK PANIN, Tbk KCU BANJARMASIN)
- THE STATEMENT OF GUARANTEES AND FINES IN SHARIA BANK FINANCING
- THE ROLE OF SHARIA AUDITORS IN THE HALAL GUARANTEE SYSTEM IN SHARIA BANK

- LEGAL PROTECTION AGAINST BANK RELATING TO THE EXECUTION OF LAND RIGHTS GUARANTEES IN MUSYARAKAH FINANCING (STUDY AT BANK BNI SYARIAH PONTIANAK BRANCH)
- JURIDICAL REVIEW OF THE RIGHT TO PENSION AS DEBT COLLECTION AT THE SAMARINDA BRANCH REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT BANK
- ASSESSMENT AND DETERMINATION OF THE TAXATIONAL VALUE OF BANK CREDIT GUARANTEE OBJECTS BASED ON LAW NUMBER 4 OF 1996 CONCERNING MONITORING RIGHTS
- BINDING OF BANK CREDIT GUARANTEES THROUGH A GUARANTEE INSTITUTION BASED ON LAW NUMBER 4 OF 1996 CONCERNING CREDIT RIGHTS
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- JURIDICAL ANALYSIS OF THE BINDING OF COLLEGE RIGHTS IN THE TAKE OVER OF CONVENTIONAL BANK CREDIT TO SHARIAH BANK (STUDY AT PT. BANK MANDIRI SYARIAH MEDAN SETIA BUDI BRANCH OFFICE)
- JURIDICAL REVIEW OF PERSONAL GUARANTEES AS GUARANTEES FOR PROVIDING CREDIT BY BANK (STUDY AT BANK BNI USU BRANCH)

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- GUARANTEE OF LEGAL PROTECTION FOR CUSTOMER DEPOSITS IN COMMERCIAL BANKS
- LEGAL POWER OF LOU AS COLLATERAL IN BANK SYNDICATION CREDITS
- IMPLEMENTATION OF PROVIDING CREDIT WITH A FIDUCIARY GUARANTEE BOUND UNDER THE HANDS (Study at PT. Bank Rakyat Indonesia (Persero) Tbk, Sukoharjo Unit, Pringsewu Branch Office)
- Legal Protection for Banks (Creditors) if Debtors Have Bad Credit with Copyright Guarantee
- Liability of the Land Office of City
- LEGAL PROTECTION OF BANK AS HOLDER OF OBJECTIVE GUARANTEES RELATED TO DEBT REPAYMENT BY DEBTORS (CASE STUDY DECISION No.50/Pailit/2010/PN.Niaga.JKT.PST)
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- PEOPLE'S BUSINESS CREDIT AGREEMENT (KUR) WITHOUT COLLATERAL BASED ON COMMANDING MINISTER REGULATION NUMBER 11 OF 2017 CONCERNING KUR IMPLEMENTATION GUIDELINES (Study at PT. Bank Rakyat Indonesia (BRI) Tugu Market Unit, Tanjung Karang Branch, Bandar Lampung)
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- EFFECTIVENESS OF THE USE OF FIDUCIARY GUARANTEES ON OBJECTS IN THE FORM OF COPYRIGHTED GOODS (STUDY IN COMMERCIAL BANKS UNDER THE SUPERVISION OF THE REGIONAL FINANCIAL SERVICES AUTHORITY IV OF THE CITY OF SURABAYA)
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- IMPLEMENTATION OF THE EXECUTION OF THE CREDIT GUARANTEE FOR BAD CREDITS OF PT. BANK ARTOS INDONESIA
- Pawning Deposits as Credit Collateral (Case Study of Solo Branch State Savings Bank)
- JURIDICAL STUDY OF OWNERSHIP CERTIFICATES AS BANK LOAN SECURITY ACCORDING TO LAW NUMBER 4 OF 1996 CONCERNING MONITORY RIGHTS TO LAND AND OBJECTS ON THE LAND AND BANKING LEGAL PERSPECTIVE
- Legal Consequences of Separating Deposits from Bank Customers During Liquidation to Obtain Collateral from the Deposit Insurance Corporation
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- Cancellation of Notarial/Ppat Grant Binding Deed Which is Still Used as Bank Loan Guarantee (Case Study of Decision of the Supreme Court of the Republic of Indonesia Number 2569 K/Pdt/2019)
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- CREDIT GUARANTEE WITH ASSIGNMENT OF MORTGAGE RIGHTS ON LAND OBJECTS AT PT. JATIM BANK
- JURIDICAL ANALYSIS OF THE CANCELLATION OF A POWER OF ATTORNEY DEED MADE BY A NOTARY'S DEED RELATED TO THE

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- Warehouse Receipts as Bank Credit Guarantee Objects (Warehouse Receipts As Bank Credit Guarantee Objects)
- LEGAL CONSEQUENCES OF THE MERGER OF SEVERAL SHARIAH BANKS ON AGREEMENTS AND GUARANTEES
- Legal Certainty of Subrogation Rights of Sharia Guarantee Companies for Financing Written Off (Write Off) by Sharia Banks (Case Study of Sharia Financing Guarantee Claims at PT Guarantee Financing Askrindo Syariah)
- IMPLEMENTATION OF WAREHOUSE RECEIPT AS CREDIT GUARANTEE AT BANK RAKYAT INDONESIA (PERSERO) Tbk. SUKOHARJO BRANCH
- LEGAL PROTECTION OF PARTIES FOR THE DESTRUCTION OF FIDUCIARY SECURITY OBJECTS IN BANK CREDIT AGREEMENTS
- Strategy for Resolving the Execution of Mortgage Rights on Collateral Objects in Murabahah Financing in Sharia Banking (Case Study: PT Bank Syariah Indonesia Medan City Area)
- EXECUTION OF CUSTOMERS' DEPENDENT RIGHTS GUARANTEES DUE TO BAD CREDIT AT PT. BANK MANDIRI SYARIAH PONTIANAK BRANCH
- Bank NTB Syariah Civil Liability Regarding Loss of Customer Credit Guarantee Documents: (Analysis of Decision Number 245/Pdt.G/2018/PN.Mtr)
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- Analysis of the Implementation of Sharia Bank Financing Guarantee Cooperation at PT. Askrindo Syariah Financing Guarantee Kc Medan
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Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 358 research topic mappings using literature studies regarding guarantees/collateral in Islamic and Conventional Financial Institutions.

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